

Dynamics of Interdependence of Drinking Water: Evidence from Water and Sanitation Service Providers (EPS) In Peru, 2017 - 2022

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ABSTRACT

The drinking water system has critical infrastructure for access and quality. The objective is to analyze the interdependence dynamics among these indicators in Peru's Water and Sanitation Service Providers (EPS) during the 2017–2022 period. Annual data from SUNASS and a VAR model were used to examine the intertemporal relationships among water coverage, service continuity, network pressure, and break density. The results indicate high persistence in the system's key variables, making rapid changes difficult; a negative influence of pipe bursts on service continuity, as evidenced by impulse-response functions; a significant short-term disconnect between access indicators (coverage) and operational quality indicators (continuity, pressure); and a pipe burst density whose component is less predictable. It is concluded that the management and regulation of the sector require a systemic approach that goes beyond evaluating isolated indicators, incorporating dynamic interrelationships to design predictive maintenance policies, strategic investment, and more comprehensive benchmarking frameworks that ensure a sustainable and equitable service.

KEYWORDS: drinking water, coverage, continuity, pressure, density.

I. INTRODUCTION

Drinking water supply systems are vital infrastructure that influences public health, economic development, and the quality of life of populations. In Latin America, about 35% of treated water is lost due to infrastructure failures, and more than 80 million people experience service interruptions (World Bank, 2025). This situation is exacerbated by climate change and rapid urban growth, which subject existing systems to pressures that increase their vulnerability.

Since 1998, the National Sanitation Services Superintendency (SUNASS) has had a policy of annually collecting control variables in its supervisory role and evaluating the control exercised by drinking water and sewerage service providers, ensuring the capacity to provide data to regulators. Due to its experience, Sunass has been designated as the leader of the Regional Benchmarking Working Group (GRTB) of the Association of Water and Sanitation Regulatory Entities of the Americas (Aderasa) since 2014, and has been recognized on more than one occasion by the International Water Association (IWA) (Sunass, 2023).

Under that regulatory framework, water and sanitation service providers (EPS) drive performance improvements by disseminating best practices identified thru management metrics to foster learning among participants and contribute to enhancing EPS performance (Heesche & Asmild, 2022). For this reason, it is important to analyze the access to and quality of sanitation services in our country, as they are considered an indispensable basic service for the quality of life of Peruvians.

The great challenge facing Water and Sanitation Service Providers (EPS) in Peru lies in understanding the complex interdependence among access and water service quality indicators, such as the amount of water distributed, service regularity, network pressure, and the frequency of physical failures. Throughout history, these indicators have been studied separately, without considering their interrelationships and how they change over time.

This fragmented approach addresses the problem of inefficient interventions, where improvements in one indicator can cause unexpected deterioration in others. This is due to a lack of knowledge about the dynamic and intertemporal relationships among the main performance variables of access and quality in water distribution systems.

In particular, it is unknown how failures and breaks propagate over time to other dimensions (such as continuity and pressure), which prevents the establishment of predictive maintenance policies and comprehensive management.

Thus, the research question arises: How are access and quality indicators dynamically related to each other in the drinking water service provided by EPSs in Peru from 2007 to 2022? Its objective is to analyze the intertemporal relationships and causal structure among drinking water access and quality indicators using a Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model, identifying patterns of persistence, feedback, and shock transmission.

International literature shows that access to safe water faces challenges that go beyond infrastructure availability, as it depends on the interplay between coverage and quality. Studies in middle- and high-income countries reveal paradoxes. In Saudi Arabia, Abubakar (2016) found that, despite the high GDP per capita and substantial investment, there are extreme territorial inequalities in water and sanitation coverage. These data indicate that national economic conditions are not sufficient to ensure equitable access; rather, it depends on local governance and regional planning.

Similarly, Molinos-Senante et al. (2019) highlight a similar situation in urban Peru: although public network coverage increased from 84% to 89% between 2013 and 2018, a significant gap still remains. Their DEA-based efficiency assessment shows that EPSs operate below their potential and that financial indicators are not associated with service quality, revealing a disconnect between operational management and outcomes for the beneficiary.

The quality and reliability facet of the service stands out as a common problem. In Nigeria, Abubakar (2016) emphasizes that the human right to water entails continuous, sufficient, and safe availability and supply in accordance with international standards. This condition conflicts with situations such as those in Kenya, where Schwartz et al. (2017) found that poor households rely on informal providers, paying more for less water of lower quality than formal prepaid alternatives. This shows how the lack of formal access creates informal markets that perpetuate inequality. In Indonesia, Roekmi et al. (2018) found a significant perception gap: citizens place the highest value on continuous (24/7) supply, yet the utility's actual performance on indicators such as water scarcity and quality is mediocre, creating a disconnect between what citizens expect and what utilities can deliver.

In Peru, the water sector faces serious difficulties following decentralization and privatization, with companies experiencing 50% losses after eight years of reforms. SUNASS's benchmarking aims to improve business performance but reveals problems such as inadequate maintenance, high levels of non-revenue water, and excess

staffing (Corton, 2003). Service quality is crucial for the sector, and its inclusion in benchmarking can improve the understanding of public performance, although total factor productivity is improving slowly (Lin, 2005).

At the macro level, Suárez-Alemán et al. (2019) found a strong correlation (between 0.78 and 0.88) between regulatory quality and government efficiency and infrastructure efficiency, with the fight against corruption and institutional strengthening being necessary conditions for improving services. At the micro level in Peru, Ioris (2012) found that variables such as network coverage and weather conditions (rain) are determinants of cost inefficiency in water and sanitation service providers (EPS), so management models should incorporate them.

Taken together, the empirical evidence suggests that water systems are complex ecosystems in which the dimensions of access and technical quality are interrelated. Isolated interventions on one indicator can negatively impact others, as anticipated by the central problem of this research. This situation creates the need for a systemic and dynamic approach to analyzing the sector.

Interdependent relationships in drinking water services are underpinned by a multidisciplinary theoretical framework that combines elements of infrastructure management, complex systems theory, and contemporary econometrics. First, the Risk-Based Asset Management Theory by Achito Quintero et al. (2020), which is the regulatory framework used. This theory proposes that optimizing the life cycle of physical assets (distribution networks) involves knowing not only their condition but also the causal and risk dependencies among their performance indicators. It anticipates that the best investment and maintenance decisions will be those that take into account systemic impacts and trade-offs, rather than isolated metrics (Achito Quintero et al., 2020). In this way, a higher failure density is not only a reactive maintenance issue but also a risk that propagates causally, affecting service continuity and pressure.

Secondly, the conceptualization of water distribution systems as Complex Adaptive Systems (Dziedzic & Karney, 2014), which provides a framework for understanding their behavior. This theoretical perspective posits that water networks, composed of multiple interrelated physical and institutional elements, exhibit emergent characteristics, nonlinearity, and feedback. In this context, there may be critical points (for example, where a small increase in pipe breaks causes a pressure collapse) and persistence patterns (for example, where a failure in one area temporarily spreads to others). Classical linear models fail to represent them, so more advanced analysis methods are needed.

Regulatory benchmarking theory, according to Carvalho et al. (2012), completes the theoretical framework by accounting for the strategic behavior of health insurance companies (EPS) within an institutional context. This theory

views comparative regulation as a repetitive learning game in which firms try to improve their performance indicators to gain regulatory advantages (e.g., tariff changes). But if benchmarking is done using metrics that don't reflect their interdependencies, it can create perverse incentives, such as improving one metric at the expense of another that isn't monitored. Therefore, a model that explains the interdependencies among indicators is essential for developing smarter, more comprehensive regulatory frameworks.

Finally, multivariate time series econometrics, particularly the vector autoregressive (VAR) theory of Trujillo Calagua (2010), is the methodological framework. This property is essential for the purpose of this research, which seeks to examine how a “shock” or change in one indicator (rupture density) propagates over time to the others (continuity, pressure), revealing mechanisms of persistence, feedback, and spillover without any prior causal assumptions.

II. METHODOLOGY

The research employs a non-experimental explanatory-correlational design and a quantitative approach, analyzing annual time series data from Peru's water and sanitation service providers (EPS) between 2017 and 2022.

The dependent variable is access to drinking water, assessed multidimensionally (social, economic, and health) using the coverage indicator. The independent variables include service quality, which is analyzed thru technical and operational indicators such as continuity, pressure, and break density, all also provided by Sunass. A VAR model was employed to understand the interdependent dynamics among the variables.

$$Y_t = c + A1Y_{t-1} + A2Y_{t-2} + \dots + ApY_{t-p} + \epsilon_t$$

Where:

Y_t is a $k \times 1$ vector of endogenous variables at time t

c is a $k \times 1$ vector of constants

The A_i are $k \times k$ coefficient matrices

ϵ_t is a $k \times 1$ vector of error terms

For this study, $k=4$ and $p=2$, resulting in a system of four equations with nine regressors each (including the constant), for a total of 36 estimated coefficients. The estimation was performed using EViews 13 software.

III. RESULTS

A. Description of the variables under analysis

In Figure 1, the drinking water access indicator for Water and Sanitation Service Providers (EPS) can be observed, with each EPS covering drinking water at varying percentages, from approximately 40%–50% (Emusap S.A., Emapacop S.A., etc.) to 90%–100% (EPS Sedachimbote

S.A., Seda Ayacucho S.A., etc.). In addition, most have high coverage (>85%), but certain rural or small populations (Emapa Huaral) have low coverage (<80%).

Figure 1: Access to drinking water from EPSs in Peru, 2017–2022 (% coverage)

Figure 2 shows that the daily hours of water service have decreased, which means that companies have reduced service time. This is due to increased demand without a corresponding increase in capacity, deficient infrastructure, droughts, climate change, and unplanned urban growth. Large urban water and sanitation companies (Sedapar, Emapat) have less than 24 hours of service. Rural water utilities (Emapa Pasco, Epssmu) provide intermittent service (less than 3 hours). While Emapa Pasco is just shy of reaching two hours of service per day.

Figure 2: Drinking water continuity of water utilities in Peru, 2017–2022 (hours/day)

Figure 3 shows the overall range of 3 for Emapa Cañete and 41 for Emapa Huancavelica. The trend generally shows adequate pressure (>15 mca). Several EPSs (Eps Grau, Emapavigs) have low pressure (<12 mca).

Figure 3: Drinking water pressure of water utilities in Peru, 2017–2022 (mca)

Figure 4 shows the rupture density, which generally ranges from -9.4 (Emsapuno 2022) to 23.6 (Emsapuno 2017); negative values are atypical and may be errors.

Figure 4: Break density of water and sanitation service providers (EPS) in Peru, 2017–2022 (breaks/km)

B. Empirical test results

The second-order autoregressive model highlights the stability and predictability of access to drinking water (l_water), with an R^2 of 98.3% and strong autoregression ($l_water(-1) = 0.907$). in terms of service quality, continuity ($l_continuity$) exhibits an r^2 of 97.2% and significant autocorrelation ($l_continuity(-1) = 0.724$), although prior outages ($l_breaks(-1) = 0.813$) have only a marginally significant impact. Water pressure ($l_pressure$) is also strongly autoregressive ($R^2 = 96.1\%$), but its relationship with continuity is only weakly significant ($l_continuity(-1) = 0.123$). the break density (l_breaks , $r^2 = 60.1\%$) indicates a complex relationship with continuity, where $l_continuity(-1)$ has a positive effect and $l_continuity(-2)$ has a negative effect. in summary, water supply stability is high, breaks affect continuity, and continuity influences pressure.

Table 1: Vector Autoregressive (VAR) Models

	l_water	$l_continuity$	$l_pressure$	l_breaks
$l_water(-1)$	0.907452 (0.05093) [17.8182]	-0.136604 (0.26650) [-0.51259]	-0.219246 (0.28755) [-0.76246]	-0.010754 (1.60168) [-0.00671]
$l_water(-2)$	0.063621 (0.04934) [1.28939]	0.071949 (0.25819) [0.27866]	0.128290 (0.27859) [0.46049]	0.524418 (1.55178) [0.33795]
$l_continuity(-1)$	-0.011821 (0.01308) [-0.90382]	0.724191 (0.06844) [10.5816]	0.123422 (0.07385) [1.67134]	0.812665 (0.41133) [1.97572]
$l_continuity(-2)$	0.012563 (0.01284) [0.97834]	0.219640 (0.06720) [3.26862]	-0.137859 (0.07251) [-1.90136]	-0.761526 (0.40386) [-1.88563]
$l_pressure(-1)$	0.006665 (0.01313) [0.50784]	0.034528 (0.06868) [0.50273]	0.845523 (0.07411) [11.4096]	-0.359507 (0.41278) [-0.87095]
$l_pressure(-2)$	-0.004497 (0.01312) [-0.34278]	-0.022833 (0.06865) [-0.33262]	0.162840 (0.07407) [2.19850]	0.404604 (0.41257) [0.98070]
$l_breaks(-1)$	-0.004249 (0.00235) [-1.80802]	-0.002933 (0.01230) [-0.23847]	0.002546 (0.01327) [0.19183]	0.548200 (0.07391) [7.41687]
$l_breaks(-2)$	0.004925 (0.00222) [2.21919]	0.002447 (0.01161) [0.21073]	-0.004994 (0.01253) [-0.39854]	0.242612 (0.06980) [3.47597]
C	0.122858 (0.04482) [2.74129]	0.432872 (0.23452) [1.84578]	0.423428 (0.25305) [1.67331]	-2.693846 (1.40949) [-1.91122]
R-squared	0.983284	0.972180	0.961305	0.601425
Adj. R-squared	0.982506	0.970886	0.959506	0.582886
Sum sq. resids	0.068897	1.886534	2.196400	68.14433
S.E. equation	0.020014	0.104729	0.113003	0.629435
F-statistic	1264.674	751.3276	534.1330	32.44214
Log likelihood	455.7362	156.1920	142.4289	-168.4212
Akaike AIC	-4.936312	-1.626431	-1.474353	1.960456
Schwarz SC	-4.777271	-1.467390	-1.315312	2.119497
Mean dependent	4.462447	2.691067	2.803067	-0.462956
S.D. dependent	0.151320	0.613788	0.561557	0.974593

Determinant	resid
covariance (dof adj.)	2.15E-08
Determinant	resid
covariance	1.75E-08
Log likelihood	589.0953
Akaike information criterion	-6.111550
Schwarz criterion	-5.475385
Number of coefficients	36

In Figure 5, breaks are the least predictable component and may require special attention to improve service continuity. The variance decomposition or impulse-response functions (IRFs) of a VAR (Vector Autoregressive) model adjusted for degrees of freedom, using Cholesky decomposition with one-standard-deviation innovations, examine how changes (shocks) in one variable influence other variables in the system over time, in the case of water services in Peru.

Figure 5: Variance decomposition analysis or impulse-response functions (IRFs) based on a VAR model

IV. DISCUSSION

Research on Peruvian water and sanitation utilities (EPS) using a VAR model reveals complex interdependencies in drinking water systems, validating a systemic approach and providing significant patterns for theory, regulation, and operational management of the sector.

The first and strongest evidence is the high inertia or persistence in all key system variables. The high coefficients of determination ($R^2 > 0.96$) for water, continuity, and pressure show that each indicator’s current value is primarily determined by its own recent past. This confirms in practice the framework of Complex Adaptive Systems (Dziedzic & Karney, 2014), in which infrastructure networks exhibit strong path dependence.

This result suggests that substantial improvements in execution are slow processes requiring ongoing interventions, and that significant changes should not be expected from isolated measures. Inertia makes it difficult to reverse accumulated damage, reflecting a negative trend at the national level. This finding is consistent with the evidence from Molinos-Senante et al. (2019) on the slow improvement in productivity at Peruvian water and sanitation service providers (EPS), demonstrating that inefficiencies tend to reinforce themselves over time.

SUNASS emphasizes the importance of proactive, long-term regulation, suggesting that annual benchmarking may not adequately reflect the system’s inertia. It proposes that improvement plans and tariff targets should consider how an EPS’s current performance is influenced by past actions and investments.

As for failure density, it is the least predictable variable ($R^2 = 0.60$), suggesting that it is influenced by unmodeled exogenous factors and serves as a source of shock propagation within the system. The dynamic relationships found are enlightening; the effect of breaks on continuity is not significant; however, the impulse-response function indicates that a positive shock to breaks results in a negative response in continuity. This supports the Risk-Based Asset Management Theory, indicating that physical failures represent an operational risk that affects service continuity, thereby justifying investments in predictive maintenance and network renewal. Low pressures cause localized hydraulic stress, and high pressures can overload aging pipelines. This highlights the need to avoid simplistic measures that increase pressure without considering the condition of the network.

With regard to coverage and operational quality, an important finding is the limited significant dynamic influence that the water coverage indicator has on quality variables (continuity, pressure) in the short term, and vice versa. Its cross-coefficients in the VAR are low and not significant. The result confirms the “access without quality paradox,” indicating that increasing network coverage does not guaranty a reliable service. It is observed that a health insurance provider (EPS) may have high accessibility but offer low intensity and discontinuous service, suggesting a disconnect between management and public policies in relation to the objectives of “universal access” and “service quality and sustainability.”

Service disconnection affects equity, as seen in Kenya, where residents of formal areas with poor service must use costly informal alternatives. In Peru, this reproduces intra-metropolitan territorial inequalities by investing in new infrastructure without improving the management of existing infrastructure.

Continuity is established as a key variable affecting various dimensions, serving as an indicator of the system’s health. Its delayed impact on pressure and its relationship to

pipe bursts link it to citizens' demand for continuous access to water, recognized as a human right (Abubakar, 2016; Roekmi et al., 2018). The presented model suggests that continuity is not only a social necessity but also a technical consequence of network conditions, which in turn influences the available pressure.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The study analyzed the interdependencies between access and drinking water service quality indicators in Peru's Water and Sanitation Service Providers (EPS) for the 2017–2022 period, using a Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model, and found:

The drinking water coverage system exhibits a strong dependence on its past values, demonstrating high persistence. This indicates that water networks function as Complex Adaptive Systems, where changes are gradual and isolated interventions have limited impacts. This inertia poses a challenge to reversing negative trends, requiring long-term strategic planning.

Service continuity is crucial, as a positive shock in failure density negatively impacts it. Although in the VAR model this relationship was not significant at all lags, the impulse-response function analysis supports the notion that physical failures are an operational risk, affecting service reliability and validating Risk-Based Asset Management.

A “paradox of access without quality” was detected, where the cross-coefficients in a VAR model show a lack of short-term dynamic influence between network coverage and operational quality indicators. This suggests that infrastructure expansion does not guaranty reliable service, highlighting a disconnect between universal access goals and service sustainability.

The break density is the most unpredictable variable in the model, affected by uncontrolled external factors that generate instability in the system.

The results suggest that it is essential to move toward more dynamic regulatory and benchmarking frameworks that go beyond evaluating isolated indicators. It is proposed to adopt a systemic perspective that considers the interrelationships between access and quality, which would enable the design of more effective incentives for predictive maintenance, network renewal, and operational management focused on service reliability. Finally, an effective policy with a systemic approach is proposed, recognizing that sustainable improvements require coordinated interventions, continuous investment in existing infrastructure, and regulation that considers the causal relationships in system performance.

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